

Multi-scale Thermal Uniformity Optimization in Methane-Fueled SOFCs

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Abstract

Methane-fueled solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) are promising energy-conversion devices due to their fuel flexibility and high efficiency. However, direct internal methane reforming causes a spatial mismatch between endothermic reforming and exothermic electrochemical reactions, leading to temperature non-uniformity, thermal stress, and durability risks. This study investigates thermal-uniformity optimization in methane-fueled SOFCs from three scales: gradient anode porosity, flow channel architecture, and thermal management. Maximum temperature difference (ΔT), temperature gradient, and peak temperature are used as the main indicators. Results show that anode porosity affects local temperature distribution, with the best case achieving $\Delta T = 4.2$ K. Flow channel modification can increase current density by 15-16%, but may also increase ΔT ; optimized trapezoidal channels reduce temperature gradient by 24%. System cooling, especially liquid cooling, shows stronger stack-level thermal regulation. These findings highlight the importance of integrated analysis in comprehensively evaluating micro-structure level, single-cell level, and system level effects on thermal uniformity.

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1. Introduction and Research Framework

1.1 Research Background

Methane-fueled solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) have attracted significant attention from both academia and industry due to their strong fuel adaptability, high energy conversion efficiency, and compact system configuration [1-2].

Figure 1. Schematic of (a) SOFC stack assembly and (b) fuel gas flow path in planar direct methane SOFC.

However, direct methane operation introduces a major thermofluid challenge: the heat absorbed by methane steam reforming in the anode is not spatially matched with the heat released by electrochemical reactions [1]. As a result, the cell may develop local hot spots, cold regions, and steep temperature gradients. These non-uniform temperature fields can generate thermal stress, damage sealing materials, accelerate anode or electrolyte degradation, and finally reduce stack durability [1-2]. Therefore, improving thermal uniformity is a key design objective for methane-fueled SOFCs and is directly related to heat transfer, reacting flow, and practical energy-system reliability.

1.2 Research Framework

This report reviews and compares multi-scale strategies for improving temperature uniformity in methane-fueled SOFCs. The analysis is organized at three levels. First, at the electrode micro-structure level, gradient anode porosity design is considered because it affects gas diffusion, reactant concentration, reforming

intensity, and local heat generation. Second, at the single-cell flow-field level, flow channel architecture is discussed because channel geometry controls fuel distribution, convective heat transfer, and reaction-zone location. Third, at the stack or system level, thermal management methods are examined because external cooling and heat redistribution are required to control large-scale temperature gradients. These three levels are connected by the same objective: reducing thermal non-uniformity and improving long-term durability.

1.3 Evaluation Metrics for Thermal Uniformity

Table 1. Thermal Uniformity Evaluation Metrics

Metrics	Explanation
ΔT	Maximum temperature difference, defined as $\Delta T = T_{max} - T_{min}$, the core intuitive indicator for evaluating the overall thermal uniformity of fuel cells.
$\frac{\partial T}{\partial L}$	Temperature gradient, characterizing the spatial variation of temperature and thermal-stress risk.
T_{max}	Peak temperature, used to characterize the extreme level of local hotspots inside the fuel cell.

To enable a consistent comparison of different optimization strategies, we adopt three thermal-uniformity indicators: maximum temperature difference (ΔT), temperature gradient ($\partial T/\partial L$), and peak temperature (T_{max}). These metrics are selected because they directly reflect the overall temperature non-uniformity, local thermal-stress risk, and hot-spot severity in methane-fueled SOFCs [1]. Their definitions and physical meanings are summarized in **Table 1**.

1.4 Review Scope

Our report focuses on journal articles published within the past three years in order to capture recent advances in the thermal optimization of methane-fueled SOFCs. The literature survey mainly covers studies related to methane-fueled SOFCs, thermal uniformity, heat redistribution, gradient anode porosity, flow channel architecture, thermal management, thermal stress, and durability. Articles were selected based on three criteria: relevance to methane-fueled SOFCs, clear connection to at least one of the three optimization scales considered in this work, and the presentation of thermal-uniformity-related findings or indicators that can support

unified comparative analysis.

Since methane-specific studies on flow channel design and system-level thermal management are still limited, this review combines methane-specific literature with transferable general SOFC studies [1]. Methane-specific evidence is used to discuss direct internal reforming and fuel-dependent thermal mismatch, while general SOFC literature is used to support broadly applicable heat-transfer, flow-distribution, and cooling mechanisms.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the methodology used to investigate thermal uniformity optimization in methane-fueled SOFCs. Three representative strategies are considered at different design scales: gradient anode porosity at the micro-structure level, flow channel architecture at the single-cell flow-field level, and thermal management at the stack level. These strategies are compared using thermal-uniformity indicators including ΔT , temperature gradient, and T_{max} , with current density used as an auxiliary performance indicator where available.

2.1 Gradient Anode Porosity Design

Gradient anode porosity is adopted as a micro-structure level strategy to regulate the coupling between gas transport, reaction distribution, and heat generation in methane-fueled SOFC anodes. Unlike a homogeneous porous anode, a graded structure allows the pore fraction to vary through the anode thickness, thereby changing effective diffusivity, permeability, and local gas accessibility [3-4]. As shown in Fig. 2, methane and steam are transported through the porous anode support layer and participate in reforming, shift, and electrochemical reactions near the active region.

The key reactions include methane steam reforming,

and water-gas shift,

govern local fuel conversion, while electrochemical oxidation,

Since these reactions depend strongly on local gas diffusion and species concentration, changing the anode porosity can redistribute reaction-active zones and reshape local heat absorption and heat generation patterns [3].

The porosity distribution is varied along the anode thickness direction, from the anode support layers (ASL) to the anode functional layers (AFL), as illustrated in Fig. 2. Six representative cases are designed to compare homogeneous and graded porosity configurations under the same numerical framework. Cases 1-3 use uniform porosity values of 0.20, 0.30, and 0.40 in ASL1, ASL2, AFL1, and AFL2, respectively. Case 6 is another homogeneous reference case with a uniform porosity of 0.27. In contrast, Cases 4 and 5 apply graded porosity, where the porosity decreases from the support side toward the functional layer near the electrolyte.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of a direct methane SOFC single cell.

The aim of this design is to evaluate the influence of porosity arrangement on transport and thermal behavior under the same modelling conditions. The six cases provided in Table 2 gives a

direct comparison between homogeneous and graded anode structures. By changing the porosity values in the ASL and AFL layers, the study examines how porosity redistribution affects methane or steam diffusion, local reaction intensity, heat generation, and temperature uniformity.

Table 2. Six Porosity distribution cases

SOFC	Porosity					
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
Anode						
ASL 1	0.20	0.30	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.27
ASL 2	0.20	0.30	0.40	0.40	0.30	0.27
AFL 1	0.20	0.30	0.40	0.30	0.20	0.27
AFL 2	0.20	0.30	0.40	0.20	0.20	0.27

2.2 Flow Channel Architecture Design

Flow channel architecture is selected as the cell-level design strategy because it directly affects methane and steam transport, convective heat transfer, reaction-zone distribution, and local heat generation in methane-fueled SOFCs [5-7]. During direct methane operation, the endothermic methane reforming reaction and the exothermic electrochemical reactions are strongly coupled with fuel distribution. Therefore, modifying the flow channel geometry can change not only the local reactant supply, but also the spatial balance between heat absorption and heat release [5].

Figure 3. Schematic cross-section of a planar SOFC single cell [7] and three flow channel cross-sections.

As shown in Fig. 3, the planar SOFC single-cell structure contains fuel and air channels separated by the anode, electrolyte, and cathode layers. In this work, three representative channel cross-sections are considered: rectangular, trapezoidal, and bow-shaped channels [7]. The rectangular channel is used as the baseline design because of its simple geometry, clear boundary, and common use in planar SOFC modelling. The trapezoidal channel modifies the upper or lower width of the gas passage, allowing the flow path to guide methane and steam more effectively toward the porous anode. Two characteristic width parameters are used to describe this design: L_a represents the lower or bottom channel width, while L_w represents the upper or top channel width. By changing L_a and L_w , the flow distribution and reactant accessibility near the anode can be adjusted [7]. The bow-shaped channel introduces a curved boundary, which reduces sharp-corner effects and provides a smoother flow transition compared with straight-edged channels.

This comparison evaluates how flow-field geometry affects fuel transport and thermal behavior, and whether enhanced reactant transport can be balanced with improved thermal uniformity under comparable modelling conditions.

2.3 Thermal Management Strategy Selection

Thermal management is selected as the stack level strategy because it needs external heat removal beyond single cell regulation. While anode porosity design and flow channel architecture mainly control local transport and reaction distribution, thermal management regulates boundary temperature and removes accumulated heat [8-9]. This is important because direct methane operation creates a mismatch between endothermic methane reforming and exothermic electrochemical reactions, which may cause hot spots, steep temperature gradients, thermal stress, and durability loss.

Figure 4. Heat transfer pathways and typical temperature gradient distribution in a planar SOFC stack [8].

As shown in Fig. 4, heat transfer in SOFC stacks involves conduction through solid components, convection between gas channels and cell surfaces, radiation at high temperature, and external heat loss or cooling. Based on these heat-transfer mechanisms, four representative cooling methods are selected for comparison: excess air cooling, independent gas cooling, liquid cooling, and heat-pipe cooling [8].

Figure 5. Typical independent cooling systems for SOFC stacks [8].

Excess air cooling uses additional air flow to remove heat from the stack. It is structurally simple and easy to control, but its cooling capacity is limited because air has relatively low heat capacity. Independent gas cooling introduces a separate cooling-gas stream, such as air or argon, to regulate the stack temperature more directly. This method provides better controllability than relying only on excess reactant air, but it may increase system volume and auxiliary power consumption [9].

Liquid cooling is selected because liquid coolants, such as pressurized water or liquid metals, have much higher heat capacity and thermal conductivity than gases. Therefore, it is suitable for high-power SOFC stacks where heat accumulation is more severe. However, liquid cooling also requires careful consideration of sealing, corrosion resistance, coolant circulation, and long-term reliability. Heat-pipe cooling is another promising strategy. It transfers heat passively from high-temperature regions to low-temperature regions through evaporation and condensation of the working fluid. For methane-fueled SOFCs, this is particularly useful because it may help balance the inlet cooling effect caused by methane reforming and the downstream heating effect caused by electrochemical oxidation [8].

Since methane-specific stack-level cooling studies are still

limited, this section selects representative thermal-management strategies from general SOFC literature and discusses their relevance to methane-fueled SOFCs through common heat-transfer mechanisms. Their effects on ΔT , temperature gradient, and thermal uniformity improvement are compared in the results section.

2.4 Simulation Procedure

The simulation procedure was established to evaluate the thermal behavior of methane-fueled SOFCs under different optimization strategies. First, a physical model of the planar single cell was constructed, including the fuel channel, air channel, anode, electrolyte, cathode, and interconnector domains. The model geometry was then modified according to different anode porosity distributions and flow channel configurations [3].

Figure 6. The coupling relationship among the various physical fields of methane-fueled SOFC.

Second, a coupled multi-physics numerical model was developed. The model considers fluid flow, species transport, heat transfer, charge transfer, chemical reactions, and electrochemical reactions, as illustrated in Fig. 6. The main governing equations include mass conservation, momentum conservation, species transport, charge conservation, and energy conservation. Methane steam reforming, water-gas shift reaction, hydrogen oxidation, and carbon monoxide oxidation were also included to describe the direct-methane operating mechanism.

Third, appropriate boundary conditions and parameter settings were applied, including inlet gas composition, flow velocity, operating temperature, outlet pressure, material properties, and electrochemical parameters [10]. These settings were kept consistent when comparing different cases, so that the influence of each design variable could be evaluated fairly.

Finally, the model was implemented and verified. Grid independence verification was conducted to reduce numerical uncertainty, and model validation was performed by comparing simulation results with reference data. After validation, temperature contours, current density, ΔT , temperature gradient, and T_{max} were extracted for further comparison.

3. Result Analysis

3.1 Thermal Effects of Anode Porosity Distribution

The simulated results under the six porosity cases indicate that anode porosity distribution affects the temperature field and thermal uniformity of methane-fueled SOFCs.

Figure 7. Temperature distribution along the cell length direction

In the central z-y longitudinal section, all cases show a similar temperature trend, with a higher temperature near the inlet and a gradual decrease toward the outlet along the cell length. This trend reflects the combined thermal effects of methane reforming, electrochemical reactions, and heat redistribution.

Taking the maximum temperature difference ΔT as the primary indicator of thermal uniformity, Case 1 exhibits the best thermal uniformity, with the lowest $\Delta T = 4.2$ K. In comparison, the ΔT values of the other cases are slightly higher: 4.5K for Case 2, 4.3 K for Case 3, 4.4 K for Case 4, 4.5 K for Case 5, and 4.4 K for Case 6.

Figure 8. Temperature distribution at the inlet x-z cross-section

The temperature distribution at the inlet x-z cross-section further shows that porosity variation also affects the transverse temperature-field characteristics near the entrance region. Some less favorable porosity configurations produce a more pronounced temperature contrast between the central channel region and the surrounding electrode domains.

Overall, anode porosity design can influence the cell temperature field by regulating gas diffusion pathways, local reactant concentration, reaction intensity, and heat-generation patterns. However, within the present parameter range, this effect is measurable but relatively moderate. Notably, the best thermal uniformity is obtained in Case 1, a homogeneous low-porosity case, rather than in the graded configurations. Therefore, gradient anode porosity should be regarded as a feasible but highly parameter-sensitive microstructural thermal-regulation strategy, whose effectiveness requires further optimization rather than simple adoption.

3.2 Thermal Effects of Flow Channel Architecture

The effects of different channel cross-sectional designs on thermal uniformity were mainly evaluated through electrolyte temperature distribution, maximum temperature difference ΔT , and temperature gradient along the cell length. In the referenced direct internal reforming methane SOFC study, the rectangular channel was used as the original baseline, while trapezoidal and bow-shaped

channels were introduced as modified cross-sectional designs. The results show that flow channel cross-section optimization does not always improve thermal uniformity directly; instead, it introduces a clear trade-off between enhanced fuel transport, electrical performance, and temperature-field uniformity [5].

Figure 9. Temperature distribution along the cell length direction under Strategy I (L_a parameter optimization) [5]

For Strategy I, both trapezoidal and bow-shaped channels improve fuel diffusion toward the anode and enhance current density when the characteristic width L_a is properly selected. The best electrical-performance improvement occurs at $L_a = 1.5W_{CH}$, with current density increasing by approximately 15.53% for the trapezoidal channel and 16.06% for the bow-shaped channel. However, this performance improvement is accompanied by a more pronounced temperature variation along the flow direction. In particular, the $L_a = 1.2W_{CH}$ case increases ΔT by nearly 7 K. Therefore, Strategy I is more effective for enhancing mass transport and electrochemical performance, but it is not necessarily beneficial for thermal uniformity [5].

Figure 10. Temperature distribution along the cell length direction under Strategy II (L_w parameter optimization) [5]

For Strategy II, the thermal behavior is different. The bow-shaped channel only provides an approximately 2% improvement in electrical performance, while increasing the overall temperature difference by about 4 K, making it less attractive from a thermal-uniformity perspective. By contrast, the trapezoidal channel in Strategy II sacrifices part of the current density, but it can reduce the temperature variation along the cell length. When $L_w = 0.52W_{CH}$, the temperature gradient is reduced by approximately 24%, indicating a more favorable temperature distribution. This suggests that trapezoidal cross-sectional modification can be a useful flow channel strategy when the design priority is temperature-field regulation rather than maximum power output [5].

Overall, the rectangular channel serves as a stable baseline, while trapezoidal and bow-shaped designs can improve fuel transport and electrochemical performance under specific conditions. However, improved reactant diffusion does not necessarily lead to better thermal uniformity. Therefore, flow channel optimization should be treated as a multi-objective problem, rather than a purely performance enhancing strategy..

3.3 Stack-level Thermal Management Results

The effectiveness of system-level thermal management can be evaluated using three indicators: maximum temperature difference ΔT , temperature gradient, and peak temperature T_{max} . Among these,

ΔT reflects the overall temperature non-uniformity of the stack, temperature variation, and T_{max} is related to local hot-spot risk. temperature gradient indicates the intensity of local spatial

Table 3. Comparison of cooling methods for SOFC stacks.

Cooling Method	Cooling Medium	Stack type and cell dimensions	Fuel composition	ΔT_{before} or $(\partial T/\partial L)_{before}$	ΔT_{after} or $(\partial T/\partial L)_{after}$
Excess air cooling	Air	40-cell planar stack, cell area 8.94×0.447 cm ²	50 % H ₂ , 50 % H ₂ O	21.4 K cm ⁻¹	14 K cm ⁻¹
Independent gas cooling	Argon (Ar), air	Tubular stack, cell length 1-5 cm	CH ₄ , CO, H ₂ , CO, H ₂ O	88.36 K	45.31 K
	Pressurized saturated water	Planar stack, cell area 9×9 cm ²	97 % H ₂ , 3 % H ₂ O	185 K	26 K
Liquid cooling	Pressurized saturated water	Tubular stack, cell length 50 cm	97 % H ₂ , 3 % H ₂ O	295 K	62 K
	Liquid tin (Sn)	Planar cell, cell area 7×7 cm ²	97 % H ₂ , 3 % H ₂ O	60 K	15 K
Heat pipe cooling	Liquid sodium (Na)	2-cell planar stack, cell area 8.8×8.8 cm ²	CH ₄ , H ₂ , H ₂ O, N ₂	43 K	15 K
	Liquid sodium	Tubular cell, cell length 10 cm	CH ₄ , CO, H ₂ , CO, H ₂ O	31 K cm ⁻¹	13 K cm ⁻¹
	Not Specific	20-cell tubular segmented-in-series stack	97 % H ₂ , 3 % H ₂ O	111 K	25 K

As shown in **Table 3**, the reviewed quantitative results show that independent cooling systems can significantly improve SOFC thermal uniformity. For liquid cooling, pressurized saturated water reduced the maximum temperature difference of a planar SOFC stack from 185 K to 26 K, and that of a tubular SOFC stack from 295 K to 62 K. Liquid-metal cooling also reduced the temperature difference of a planar cell from 60 K to 15K, indicating strong capability for rapid heat removal and large-scale temperature-field flattening.

Heat-pipe cooling also shows strong potential. In a planar SOFC stack, heat-pipe integration reduced ΔT from 43 K to 15 K. In a tubular SOFC, the axial temperature gradient was reduced from 31 Kcm⁻¹ to 13 Kcm⁻¹. In a 20-cell segmented tubular SOFC stack, heat-pipe integration reduced the maximum temperature difference from 111K to 25K. These results suggest that heat pipes are effective in both reducing ΔT and redistributing heat along the stack length.

Overall, system-level thermal management is a necessary complement to anode porosity design and flow channel optimization. Liquid cooling and heat-pipe-assisted cooling show the strongest

potential for stack-level thermal uniformity improvement. However, most reported cases are based on general SOFC systems rather than methane-fueled SOFC stacks. Their application in methane-fueled SOFCs still requires methane-specific validation, because direct internal reforming introduces stronger spatial thermal imbalance and high-temperature engineering constraints.

4. Conclusion and Future Work

4.1 Conclusion

The key findings of the three optimization strategies are summarized and compared in **Table 4**.

At the micro-structure level, the six anode porosity cases show that porosity distribution can change local temperature distribution in methane-fueled SOFCs. Case 1 gives the best thermal uniformity, with the lowest $\Delta T = 4.2K$. The graded cases are feasible, but their effect is parameter-sensitive, so gradient anode porosity should not be treated as automatically better than homogeneous porosity.

Table 4. Summary of Multi-scale Optimization Strategies and Key Findings

Optimization scale	Optimization strategy	Key findings
Micro-structure level	Gradient anode porosity design	Case 1 gives the best thermal uniformity, with the lowest $\Delta T = 4.2K$.
Single-cell level	flow channel design	Trapezoidal and bow-shaped channels enhance current density by 15-16%; Strategy II trapezoidal modification reduces the temperature gradient by 24%.
System level	System-level thermal management	Independent cooling systems reduce ΔT and suppress temperature gradients; liquid cooling reduces the maximum temperature difference from 185 K to 26 K.

At the single cell flow-field level, channel geometry produces a stronger performance thermal uniformity trade-off. Specific trapezoidal and bow-shaped channels enhance current density by 15-16%, but intensified local reactions can increase ΔT by nearly 7 K. When temperature regulation is prioritized, the Strategy II trapezoidal modification reduces the temperature gradient by 24%, although part of the electrical performance is sacrificed.

At the stack or the system level, thermal management provides the strongest global temperature-field flattening. Independent cooling systems can effectively reduce ΔT and suppress large-scale temperature gradients. In particular, liquid cooling reduces the maximum temperature difference from 185 K to 26 K in a planar SOFC stack, showing thermal uniformity improvement.

Overall, these three strategies are complementary. Anode porosity and flow channel design adjust local diffusion, reaction, and heat-generation pathways, but their improvements are moderate and

design-dependent. System-level cooling is therefore needed as an external complement. Together, multi-scale optimization supports better thermal uniformity and long-term durability.

4.2 Future Work

Thermal uniformity optimization in methane-fueled SOFCs requires balancing trade-offs across three scales. Anode porosity design can regulate local gas diffusion and reaction distribution, but is highly parameter-sensitive. Flow channel architecture improves fuel transport and current density, but may increase ΔT and reduce thermal uniformity. System-level cooling suppresses large-scale temperature gradients, but may add system complexity and reliability issues. Future work should focus on methane-specific thermal management, cross-scale coupling among these strategies, and evaluation including thermal uniformity, long-term durability, manufacturing cost, and practical system integration.

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Appendix A: Grid independence verification of 2.1

Figure. A3 Schematic diagram of mesh partitioning

Figure. A4 Verification of grid independence

Appendix B: Supplementary Simulation Results of 3.1

Figure A1. Effect of anode porosity on average cell temperature and chemical reaction rates.

Figure A2. Current density distribution along the cell length under six porosity cases.

Appendix C: Work Distribution

Name	Photo	UCD Number	Work Distribution
Weihao Chen		23219291	Team leader and project coordinator; Clarified course requirements; Developed the overall report framework and poster structure; Coordinated task allocation; Conducted COMSOL multi-physics simulation and case comparison; Analyzed temperature distribution, current density, and thermal uniformity indicators; Prepared key figures, tables, and data visualizations; Led report writing, poster layout, final revision, and overall quality checking.
Yixin Gao		23219352	Reviewed literature on gradient anode porosity; Organized anode structure and porosity design cases; Analyzed effects on gas diffusion and reaction distribution; Assisted with simulation result analysis; Wrote the gradient anode section of the report; Assisted with poster figures and content preparation; Poster making and report writing.
Shengyao Wang		23219325	Reviewed literature on flow channel optimization; Built 3D physical models using SolidWorks; Organized flow channel diagrams, methodology visuals, and result figures; Participated in preparing the flow-channel schematic diagrams, methodology flowchart, and results presentation for the poster.
Ziqiao Zhou		23219342	Reviewed literature on thermal management and cooling strategies; Organized gas cooling, liquid cooling, and heat-pipe cooling methods; Assisted with poster design, cooling tables, references, and formatting.